

CARBON NANOTUBE (CNT)-ALUMINUM: TOWARDS CNT-REINFORCED ALUMINUM CONDUCTOR CABLES

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Keywords: *carbon nanotubes, aluminum, metal matrix composites, nanocomposites, electrical resistivity, power transmission, ACSR cable*

1 Introduction

Individual carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have remarkable properties including high strength, flexibility, and thermal and electrical conductivities. Based on these properties, CNT-enabled materials including CNT-filled composites and assemblies of CNTs (e.g., sheets, arrays and fibers) are of interest for a wide range of applications. The potential to use CNTs for power cables has generated considerable excitement. Nobel laureate Richard Smalley's vision for CNTs included an *armchair quantum wire*, composed of a particular chirality of metallic single-walled CNTs (SWCNTs), that would revolutionize the electrical grid [1,2]. Important steps have recently been made towards this goal with advances in CNT fibers [3] and coaxial cables [4,5], and isolation and amplification of specific SWCNT chiralities [6,7]; however, such a cable remains a long-term vision.

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) incorporating CNTs, specifically CNT-aluminum (CNT-Al), may also offer an intermediate term solution to improve on present power cable technology. Standard high voltage transmission lines employ ACSR (aluminum conductor steel reinforced) cables, in which the steel provides strength but adds significant weight (often > 30% [8]) and does not contribute to conduction. CNT-aluminum composites have been prepared by a variety of conventional methods, including powder metallurgy and melting as well as more exotic techniques [9]. In various cases, addition of CNTs to aluminum (Al) has been shown to improve strength [9]. However, aluminum carbide (Al_4C_3) is often

formed at the interfaces and few studies have looked at the electrical resistivity of CNT-Al composites, which would be expected to increase in cases of Al_4C_3 formation.

Our goal is to develop CNT-reinforced aluminum composites with electrical and mechanical properties that will enable substantially greater transmission capability than traditional ACSR. We have achieved successful production of aluminum and SWCNT-Al MMCs, containing up to 5 wt% raw SWCNTs, from powder. Where formation of Al_4C_3 was successfully inhibited, the conductivity of the composites was comparable to pure aluminum. By using a silver coating to protect the SWCNTs, the amount of Al_4C_3 formed was undetectable by X-ray diffraction. In a preliminary test, the ultimate tensile strength of this sample also was significantly improved.

2 Application Assessment

On the hypothesis that a well-integrated CNT-Al composite will provide equal conductivity and improved strength in comparison to the Al strands in existing cables, a basic assessment of the strength improvement required to eliminate the steel core has been performed. From Table 1, which compares the specifications of existing cables ("Drake" & "Lilac") to hypothetical CNT-reinforced cables (AC[CNT]R) with assumed 50%-100% higher Al strand strength, it can be seen that strength improvements over 50% offer potential to eliminate the steel and provide equal or better strength/weight and lower resistance (R_{AC}). This is considered to be a realistic target, based on the CNT-Al literature [9], and is likely a

Table 1. Specifications of example cables for all aluminum conductor (AAC) and ACSR cables from Southwire.com [8], and projected specifications of CNT-reinforced cables based on assuming an improvement of the Al strand strength by 50% to 100% (1.5x to 2x) with maintained density and electrical properties relative to the AAC example. Cables of with: (a) the steel strands removed, (b) the steel strands replaced with additional CNT-Al strands, and (c) the same weight as the ACSR example, are considered.

Type/Name	Strand diameter (in)		Weight / 1000 ft (lbs)			Strength (lbs)	R _{AC} / 1000 ft (Ohms)
	Al	Steel	Al	Steel	Total		
AAC/“Lilac”	61 x 0.1142	0	745	0	745	14,300	0.0217
ACSR/“Drake”	26 x 0.1749	7 x 0.1360	749	344	1093	31,500	0.0214
Assumed 1.5x existing Al strand strength:							
(a) AC[CNT]R	26 x 0.1749	0	745	0	745	21,400	0.0217
(b) AC[CNT]R	33 x 0.1749	0	945	0	945	27,200	0.0171
(c) AC[CNT]R	61 x 0.1383	0	1093	0	1093	31,500	0.0148
Assumed 2x existing Al strand strength:							
(a) AC[CNT]R	26 x 0.1749	0	745	0	745	28,600	0.0217
(b) AC[CNT]R	33 x 0.1749	0	945	0	945	36,300	0.0171
(c) AC[CNT]R	61 x 0.1383	0	1093	0	1093	41,900	0.0148

conservative estimate of the improvement as it does not consider the potential to improve electrical properties, in particular due to the high amapacy of CNTs. The example uses a “Drake” ACSR cable as it one of the most commonly used transmission line conductors, and an AAC cable with a similar amount of Al. However, the general conclusions apply to other cables with a similar percentage of steel.

The materials cost for CNT-Al also has been considered. Using the current price of SWCNTs from Raymor Nanotechnologies (\$10/g) [10], the materials cost for a cable containing 1 wt% SWCNTs would be ~50x that of the ACSR cable based on current Al prices. While the present cost is high, a CNT cost of \$0.1/g, which is representative of present costs for industrial-scale multi-walled CNTs and a feasible cost for larger industrialization of SWCNTs in the future, gives a materials cost only ~1.5x that of ACSR. Such a premium is likely acceptable considering that a lighter weight cable (per unit of power transmitted) will significantly reduce infrastructure costs.

3 Preparation and Characterization Methods

3.1 CNT Integration

Metal matrix composites were produced using

SWCNTs grown by a laser vaporization method at the National Research Council [11], and commercial aluminum powder. The SWCNTs were integrated into the aluminum powder by solvent processing, involving sonication to de-bundle SWCNTs in solvent and homogenize the SWCNTs within the aluminum powder, followed by recovery of a SWCNT-Al powder. Variations of two powder metallurgy processes: hot isostatic pressing (HIP) and sintering, which involved somewhat different CNT integration steps, were employed to consolidate the powers into solid composites.

3.2 Consolidation by Hot Isostatic Pressing

The first strategy involved consolidation of the CNT-Al composite by HIP and is shown schematically in Figure 1. Two approaches, using unmodified SWCNTs and silver-coated SWCNTs (Ag@SWCNTs) were used. The silver-coating method consisted of a hydroxyl functionalization followed by reaction with Ag nanoparticles. This metal coating strategy was employed as Ag has been observed to inhibit carbide formation in CNT-titanium composites [12], and therefore offers an additional route to prevent undesirable Al₄C₃ formation, and functionalization also promotes dispersion of the SWCNTs.

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Fig 1. Schematic of the SWCNT-Al composite preparation for HIP-consolidated samples. Two integration approaches, with and without a silver nanoparticle coating to protect against Al₄C₃ formation, are shown along with cross-sections cut from the consolidated composites.

For HIP-consolidation, pure aluminum powder or a SWCNT-Al powder was first packed into a ¾” Al-6063 tube. The atmospheric gasses were then evacuated from the vessel and it was sealed under vacuum leaving only the desired material constituents. The vessel was then subjected to high pressure and temperature (up to 30,000 psi and 600 °C in cases) within the HIP chamber to compress the powder and forge it into a solid. An advantage of this method of forging is that the metallic powder is forged into a solid at an elevated temperature while remaining below the melting temperature, allowing for temperature to be optimized to address factors such as Al₄C₃ formation, CNT damage and

dispersion. Following HIP-consolidation, the ends of the sample were cut off and it was swaged through a series of dies. By including heat treatments between swaging steps it was possible to swage down to a diameter of 0.188 inches without observable cracking. An example showing the as-consolidated material before and after swaging is shown in Figure 2. Note that the interface between the inner aluminum or CNT-Al composite and the outer Al-6063 shell remains continuous after swaging. This illustrates another advantage of the HIP method: that a material consisting of a CNT-Al composite surrounded by an Al or Al alloy shell can be prepared in a single step.

Before HIP

3/4" Al-6063 tube packed with powder and sealed

After HIP (and cut)

After swaging

Fig 2. HIP-consolidated SWCNT-Al composites before and after swaging. Note the contrast between the darker SWCNT-Al composite in the center of the cross-section and the lighter colored Al-6063 shell. Importantly, the interface between the MMC and the outer Al-6063 shell remains continuous after swaging.

Fig 3. Schematic of SWCNT-Al composite preparation for sintered samples along with a picture of a sintered disk and SEM images of fracture surfaces of SWCNT-Al composites.

3.3 Consolidation by Sintering

The second strategy involved consolidation of the CNT-Al composite by sintering and is shown schematically in Figure 3. A limitation of the previous HIP method is it is a batch process. The sintering method employed here involves proprietary processes of CanmetMATERIALS and is scalable to large volume, an important consideration given the application target. In this approach, the SWCNTs were first dispersed into Proflow 3000 to prepare a 5 wt% SWCNT composite. This composite was one ingredient in a proprietary mixing process that also included pure aluminum powder and paraffin wax, a standard binder for sintering processes. The green mixture was shaped into a disk approximately 19 mm in diameter and 4 mm in thickness and sintered to form a metal matrix composite. Both Proflow 3000 and paraffin wax are burnt off in the process. By controlling the sintering conditions, consolidated samples of both pure aluminum and SWCNT-Al composites with densities greater than 99% of that of the theoretical density of aluminum were obtained.

3.4 Characterization

Compositional analysis employed X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements (Bruker AXS D8 Advance X-ray diffractometer) on solid SWCNT-Al composites and baseline aluminum samples, after powder consolidation, with profile matching to check for the presence of Al_4C_3 . The samples were machined to obtain the required thickness and a flat surface. For polycrystalline samples without a preferred orientation, XRD spectra show the expected peaks from all crystal orientations such as is observed for a powder sample. The experimental spectra were fitted using *FullProf Suite* and compared to calculated spectra for aluminum and Al_4C_3 .

Electrical resistivity of the HIP-consolidated samples was determined from measurements on 5 mm diameter swaged rods using a Keithley 2602 source-measure unit. Due to their low resistance, a 4-probe configuration and current-reversal were employed to eliminate lead/contact resistance and voltage offset errors. In addition, a range of voltage lead separations (from 3 to 30 cm) were tested and

checked for consistency. Uniaxial tensile tests also were performed on selected samples to evaluate strength. The tests were performed on swaged rods of constant cross-section (~5 mm diameter) and the metal matrix composite was compared to a baseline aluminum sample of the same geometry. The tensile tests were performed at 200 °C, which is a typical operating specification for a high voltage transmission cable. For sintered samples, the electrical resistivity also was measured by a 4-probe method, in that case using an ULVAC ZEM3 measuring system.

4 Results & Discussion

4.1 Compositional Analysis

XRD spectra of the baseline and CNT-Al MMCs are shown in Figure 4. The spectrum from an aluminum sample, which was produced using the HIP process from the same Al-1000 powder used for composite preparation, shows the peaks characteristic of aluminum and was used as a baseline for comparison to the composites. Spectra for the initial SWCNT-Al composites (SWCNT-Al-v1) produced by HIP showed extensive formation of Al_4C_3 . This is indicated by the presence of many additional peaks, which are not observed in the spectrum for the baseline aluminum sample, with the expected positions and relative intensities for aluminum carbide. The spectra are shown on a logarithmic scale in order to show the lower intensity peaks. For the subsequent spectra shown in Figure 4, the intensity of Al_4C_3 peaks is greatly reduced. It is evident from the XRD spectrum of a second sample produced from the same SWCNT-Al powder (SWCNT-Al-v2) that, through optimization of the HIP consolidation, it was possible to inhibit formation of Al_4C_3 . In that case only the most diagnostic of the carbide peaks, indicated by arrows in Figure 4, were observed above the background. A very similar spectrum is observed for the sample produced by the sintering method, although in that case the final SWCNT content is lower.

The least instance of Al_4C_3 formation was observed for the silver-protected SWCNT composite (Ag@SWCNT-Al), which was produced by HIP, where the XRD spectrum does not show any evidence of Al_4C_3 formation as even the most

Fig 4. XRD data (○) and fit (—). The calculated peak positions for aluminum (I) and aluminum carbide (II) are indicated below each spectrum. The aluminum carbide phase is included only for the sample SWCNT-AI-v1, as this is the only case with extensive aluminum carbide formation. In other cases, either only the most intense aluminum carbide peaks are observed (HIP: SWCNT-AI-v2 and Sintering: SWCNT-AI) or no aluminum carbide peaks above the background (HIP: Ag@SWCNT-AI). Note that the aluminum spectrum shown for comparison was for a sample produced by the HIP method.

intense Al_4C_3 peaks are not observable above the background. The relative decrease in the Al_4C_3 :Al ratio in comparison to SWCNT-AI-v2, which was produced with the same HIP conditions, also could be due to its lower SWCNT content. Although both composites contained ~5wt% filler, the majority of

the filler weight for Ag@SWCNT-AI was silver and the composite contained only 0.5 wt% SWCNT. Considering the XRD spectra obtained for the four types of MMC shown in Figure 4, results show that it was possible to inhibit formation of aluminum carbide by controlling the processing conditions

used for preparation of the SWCNT-Al composites, in both the HIP and sintering methods, and through the use of a silver coating. It is clear that the silver protection scheme was effective in preventing carbide formation; however, the protective coating step may not be essential as Al_4C_3 formation was also inhibited in other cases. A comparison of samples with and without the Ag coating but with equal SWCNT content, which was not part of the current set, would conclusively determine if the silver coating provides a significant benefit. However, performance measures including electrical resistivity and strength are more important at this stage to determine if the amount of Al_4C_3 produced is tolerable for potential transmission cable applications.

4.2 Physical Properties

Electrical resistivity results for aluminum and the CNT-Al MMCs are shown in Table 2. Duplicate samples were tested using several measurement currents ($i = 0.1$ to 1 A) and voltage lead separations ($L = 3$ to 30 cm) to verify that the resistivity results were consistent. Samples with extensive Al_4C_3 evident in the XRD spectra had high resistivity, three orders of magnitude higher than aluminum. In contrast, when Al_4C_3 formation was inhibited the resistivity was only a small factor higher than the baseline aluminum samples without SWCNTs.

In a preliminary mechanical test the ultimate tensile strength of the Ag@SWCNT-Al composite, which showed the least incidence of Al_4C_3 and the lowest resistivity of the HIP-consolidated samples, was tested and found to be an average of 70% higher (1.7x) than that of an aluminum sample produced by HIP (120 MPa vs. 70 MPa). Three MMC samples were tested along with three baseline aluminum samples. While these MMCs also contained silver, based on simple rule of mixtures estimates the strength increase due to addition of silver would be expected to be much less than observed for the Ag@SWCNT-Al MMC. Therefore, it can be concluded that the SWCNT integration is crucial to the strength-improvement observed here.

While the absolute strength values are below typical AAC and ACSR cables, there are a number of post-consolidation treatments that are known to improve the mechanical performance of aluminum. Additionally, an aluminum alloy powder could be employed instead of pure aluminum. Power transmission aluminum alloy (Al-1350-H19) because it provides higher strength than pure aluminum. While none of these methods were within the scope of the work, they indicate ample opportunity to improve the strength.

5 Conclusions

Production of aluminum and SWCNT-aluminum MMCs, containing up to 5 wt% raw SWCNTs,

Table 2. Electrical resistivity at room temperature for aluminum and SWCNT-Al metal-matrix composites prepared by the HIP and sintering methods

Sample	Production method	wt% SWCNTs	Electrical resistivity (Ω cm)
Aluminum (literature)	NA	0	2.8×10^{-6}
Aluminum (this study)	HIP	0	3.1×10^{-6}
SWCNT-Al-v1	HIP	5	5.8×10^{-3}
SWCNT-Al-v2	HIP	5	5×10^{-6}
Ag@SWCNT-Al (Ag:SWCNT= 10:1)	HIP	0.5	3.7×10^{-6}
Aluminum (this study)	Sintering	0	3.1×10^{-6}
SWCNT-Al	Sintering	0.66	3.2×10^{-6}

from powder has been reported. Where the formation of Al_4C_3 was successfully inhibited, the conductivity of the metal matrix composites was comparable to pure aluminum samples. In a preliminary test, the ultimate tensile strength also was significantly improved relative to a baseline aluminum sample prepared by the same method.

Considering the electrical resistivity and strength values observed here, along with the estimated percentage improvements required to replace the steel strands in conventional ACSR cables and the potential avenues for further improvement, these initial results are encouraging in terms of the potential to produce CNT-reinforced aluminum conductor cables and merit further investigation.

Acknowledgements

This work was funded in part through the NRCan ecoENERGY initiative and supported by the National Research Council Canada (NRC), Natural Resources Canada (NRCan), and the University of British Columbia. Technical assistance from Stephane Dénommée (NRC) for sample machining and discussions with Gary Enright (NRC) regarding X-ray diffraction analysis are gratefully acknowledged.

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